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Improvement of the Civil Service Legislation in the Conditions of Power Restart in Ukraine: innovations and risks

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of innovations and risks of the amendments to the legislation on the civil service in the conditions of restarting power in Ukraine. It is established that the innovations relate to the scope of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service", legal bases of the civil service, management of the civil service, entry into the civil service, its passage and suspension. In order to evaluate these innovations of the current Law on Civil Service of Ukraine, the method of SWOT analysis was applied. SWOT Analysis of the Civil Service Law of Ukraine allowed to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment of the changes and innovations that contribute to the improvement of the civil service legislation and cause threats and risks in the civil service, to identify as potential threats and the risks arising from the introduction of innovations, as well as the potential of the external environment to address them by further improving the civil service legislation to improve its quality and effectiveness and, adherence to European standards for the protection of human rights in the public service. Among the risks and threats of the changes were the following: substantial violations of the constitutional rights and freedoms of civil servants, discrimination and narrowing of their rights, violation of the Recommendations of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe to the member states of the Council of Europe on the status of public servants in Europe of Ukraine "On Civil Service".

1 Introduction

In the conditions of modernization of civil service and public administration reform of Ukraine, an important event for improvement of the legislation on public service was the adoption of the law of Ukraine "On some amendments to laws of Ukraine concerning the restart of the power" from September 19, 2019 No. 117-IX [1], which introduced amendments to some legislative acts, in particular, to the existing in the country from May 2016, the law of Ukraine "On civil service" [2].

The proposed changes concern the narrowing of the scope of the Law of Ukraine "On civil service" and the limitations of labor legislation on public service; clarification of legal framework of public service, including the facilitation of entry into the civil service, the introduction of the possibility of contract of public service, improvement of procedure of civil service and dismissal from it, increasing the responsibility of public officials for the achievement of their performance; improving the system of management of the civil service, including by clarifying the authority of the governing bodies, to eliminate unnecessary intermediate bodies appeal, while maintaining an unconditional right to judicial appeal, etc [1, 2].

However, based on the analysis of these changes must be stated, that in some cases improvement of the law of Ukraine "On civil service" [2] in terms of the restart of power contributes to a significant violation of constitutional rights and freedoms of civil servants, discrimination and narrowing of the scope of their rights, contrary to the Recommendations of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe member States of the Council of Europe

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"On the status of public servants in Europe" [3]. Thus, the relevance of this problem is undeniable. In addition, today there are no comprehensive publications on the analysis of the innovations and risks of changes to the Law of Ukraine "On civil service" [1, 2] in terms of the restart of power that led to the selection of the chosen perspective of the study.

2 Presentation of the main results

Consider specifically the innovations that have been made to date in the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine on Restarting Power" [1, 2], in particular:

1. Scope of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service".

The amendments supplemented the list of persons who are not covered by the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" (Article 3, part 3).

2. Legal principles of the civil service.

1) The division of civil service positions in public bodies into categories and subcategories is foreseen depending on the order of appointment, nature and scope of authority, content of work and its influence on making the final decision, the degree of official responsibility, the required level of qualification and professional competencies of civil servants. It is established that the definition of subcategories of civil service positions and the equalization of civil service positions is carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine upon submission of the central executive body, which ensures the formation and implementation of state policy in the sphere of public service (Article 6 of the Law).

2) The list of persons classified into the categories of civil service posts "A", "B" and "V" (part two of Article 6 of the Law) has been supplemented.

3. Management of the civil service.

1) Additional powers are given to the central executive body, which provides for the formation and implementation of state policy in the field of public service, namely: 17-1) provides and implements the development, implementation and technical support of information, telecommunication and information and telecommunication systems and technologies in the field within his competence; 17-2) organize a centralized assessment of the professional competencies of candidates during the competition for civil service positions in accordance with the procedure established by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine; 17-3) administers the Unified Civil Service Job Portal. At the same time, the powers to carry out checks on the observance of the civil service legislation, protection of the rights of civil servants in the adoption, passage and termination of the civil service, development and approval of training programs for public servants are excluded.

2) The powers of the Commission of the Senior Civil Service Corps on the selection of candidates for the post of civil service of category "A" have been reduced (Articles 15, 16).

4. Entry into the Civil Service.

1) Requirements for persons applying for civil service have been clarified: for positions in category "V" there is a degree of higher education of at least a junior bachelor or bachelor by decision of the subject of destination, fluency in the state language; stated that the special requirements for persons applying for public service positions of categories "B" and "V" should be determined by the subject of appointment, taking into account the recommendations approved by the central executive body, which ensures the formation and implementation of public policy in the field of public service (v. 20).

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2) The procedure for holding a competition for public service positions has been improved, defining the constituents of the procedure for holding a competition (Article 22), additional conditions for publishing information about its holding, limiting the period of submission of information for participation in the competition to at least 7 and not more than 30 calendar days from the day of publication of information about the competition, as well as improving the organization of the creation and holding of the competition commission (Article 27), registration and publication of the results of the competition - not later than 45 calendar days from the date of publication of the information. rationale for its conduct (Article 23; Article 28); supplementing the information for participation in the competition (Article 25); granting the deferred right of the subject of appointment to re-determine the winner of the competition for the civil service (Article 29) and specifying the conditions for holding the re-competition (Article 30).

3) Improved the procedure for appointment to the position of civil service (Article 31), including the introduction of a contractual form of civil service (Articles 31-1); clarifying the requirements for the urgent appointment to public service of categories "A", "B" and "V" (Article 34), as well as testing and establishing the suitability of a civil servant to a position (Article 35), the application of deferred law of the subject of appointment to re-determine the winner of the competition in case of refusal of the person to take the Oath (Art. 36), etc.

5. The passage of the public service.

1) Improved procedures for the transfer of a public servant without the required competition (article 41) of significant changes in terms of the public service, reducing the period of notice of a state employee about significant change in terms of public service up to 30 calendar days (was two months) (article 43); improved procedure for evaluating the performance of civil servants (including the introduction of contractual forms of public service), which is based on indicators of efficiency, effectiveness and quality determined according to official duties a public servant, as well as compliance with rules of ethical conduct and legal requirements in the field of preventing corruption, the implementation of individual professional development programs, as well as indicators identified in the contract about passing of the state service (in the case of imprisonment) (article 44); enrollment in the experience of public service, adding to it the time of passing the diplomatic service in diplomatic posts, the posts foster service, etc (article 46), established a procedure to inform the public servant of information or documents by delivery or the sending by mail, including with the use of other means of telecommunication (article 9-1).

2) Made changes in the terms of remuneration of public servants (articles 50, 52), defining among the types of state employee premiums: 1) premium according to the annual evaluation of performance; 2) a monthly or quarterly bonus in accordance with the personal contribution of the civil servant in the overall performance of the public body; 3) a monthly or quarterly prize for the proper execution of the contract on passage of public service (in case) and setting the limitation that the total amount of premiums that may be acquired by a state employee for the year may not exceed 30 percent of the Fund his salary for the year (article 50) and noting that the bonus Fund of the state body is set at 20 percent of total Fund salaries for the year and saving of the wage Fund (article 52).

3) Simplified procedure of accountability civil servant to disciplinary liability and appeal decisions to impose disciplinary sanctions (articles 66-69, 71-73, 78), namely: changed requirements to the members of the disciplinary Committee, which from now on shall be comprised of not less than three members and not six, as expected the previous version of the law (article 69); excluded from the disciplinary Commission of representatives of public associations, representatives of elected body of primary trade Union organization of government employees or representatives of public officials, elected at the General meeting (conference) of civil servants (which were before) (article 69); article 70 "the General meeting (conference) of civil servants of the state organ" has been removed altogether from the Law as excluded article 71 of the "internal investigation". In the new edition of the Law article

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71 provides for the implementation of disciplinary proceedings under the procedure approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, which should define in particular: powers and procedure of work of the disciplinary Commission; the procedure for the formation of the disciplinary Commission; procedure for disciplinary proceedings in case of impossibility of creation or the functioning of the disciplinary Commission of a public authority etc.

4) Limited effect of labour legislation on public service, envisaging that "the rules of labour legislation do not apply to government servants, except in cases expressly stipulated by Law".

5) Made changes for the features of the public service in some public bodies (articles 91, 92).

6. Termination of public service.

1) The grounds on which the civil service is terminated (Articles 83, 84, 85, 87, 87-1, 88-1), including: on the initiative of the subject of appointment (Articles 87, 87-1 of this Law); on the grounds envisaged by the civil service contract (in case of conclusion) (Article 88-1 of the Law). Among the additional grounds for termination of civil service of individual civil servants at the initiative of the subject of appointment (Art. 87-1) is the decision of the subject to appoint a decision on dismissal of a civil servant from the post of a civil service of category "A" on his own initiative, on the submission of Prem ' the Prime Minister of Ukraine or the relevant Minister or Head of the Central Executive Body (Head of the State Authority) within four months of the appointment of the Prime Minister of Ukraine or the relevant Minister or Head of Central tion executive body (the head of the public body) with simultaneous admission of such public servant for the state of the relevant authorities.

To assess these innovations of the law of Ukraine "On civil service" [2] is applicable one of the most effective methods – the SWOT analysis.

The main advantage of the SWOT analysis, in comparison with other methods is the possibility of processing large amount of information to determine the current status and directions of development of object of research; however, due to the application of the procedure for the dichotomous analysis, it is possible to obtain an accurate qualitative assessment of internal and external factors that both positively and negatively influence functioning and development of the studied object [4, p. 114].

Using the method of SWOT-analysis for the evaluation of innovations for improving the Law of Ukraine "On state service" after the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On amendments to some laws of Ukraine concerning the restart of the power" it should be noted that in this context, the acronym SWOT stands for the following: S – Strength – a strong hand the changes and innovations that contribute to improving the legislation on public service; W – Weaknesses – weaknesses of these innovations, which are the cause of the threats and risks in the public service arising from the changes; O – Opportunities – potential for improvement of the legislation on public service with the aim of improving its efficiency and quality; T – Threats – potential threats and risks that arise as a result of innovations of the law on civil service in the conditions of the restart of power and which require immediate removal.

Model of SWOT-analysis for assessing innovations for improving the Law of Ukraine "On state service" in terms of the restart of power shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Model of SWOT-analysis for assessing innovations for improving the Law of Ukraine "On state service" in terms of restarting the government.

The model indicated that the input for the analysis innovations are the amendments to the Law of Ukraine "On state service" in terms of the restart of power and factors of the analysis of the amendments, which include the scope of the Law of Ukraine "On civil service", the legal basis of the public service management public service enter public service, its passage and termination [1, 2].

SWOT-analysis of the innovations of the law of Ukraine "On civil service" [2] involves identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment changes and innovations, which contribute to improving the legislation on public service and the threats and risks in the public service, identifying both the potential threats and risks which arose as a result of innovations and potential opportunities of the external environment to eliminate them by further improvement of the legislation on public service to improve its quality and efficiency, compliance with European standards of human rights protection in the public service.

That is, the output of this model are the results of the analysis of the external and internal environment of the adopted innovations, identification of risks and threats in the public service and defining ways and mechanisms of their elimination and resolution through the further improvement of the legislation.

The analysis of the internal environment has allowed us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the innovations of the law of Ukraine "On civil service" [1, 2]. (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Analysis of the internal environment of innovations of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" [1, 2].

S – Strength	W – Weaknesses
1. The process of civil service management was improved by optimizing the functions of the National Agency of	1. Among the responsibilities of NADS excluded powers (article 13) in respect of: carrying out checks of observance of the legislation on public service; protect the rights of public servants when receiving, passing and the termination of public service, in particular regarding the appeal of decisions of state bodies deprived of the authority to review such complaints. Reduced the powers of the Commission of senior civil service on the selection of candidates for positions of public service category "A" (articles 15, 16), which

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<p>Ukraine for Civil Service (NADS).</p> <p>2. The procedure for holding a competition for public service positions has been improved.</p> <p>3. A contractual form of civil service was introduced (Art. 31-1).</p> <p>4. The requirements for the urgent appointment to the civil service of categories "A", "B" and "B" (Article 34), as well as the testing and establishment of the suitability of a civil servant to the position (Article 35), have been clarified.</p> <p>5. The procedure of passing the civil service has been improved.</p> <p>6. The procedure for bringing a civil servant to disciplinary responsibility and appealing against the decision to impose disciplinary sanctions are simplified (Articles 66-69, 71-73, 78).</p> <p>7. The grounds for termination of public service were terminated (Articles 83, 84, 85, 87, 87-1, 88-1).</p>	<p>contributes to direct or indirect political influence on the appointment of candidates for senior management positions in the public service.</p> <p>2. Created the conditions for the adoption of the head of the sole subjective decision on the appointment of the winner among five candidates proposed by the Commission the competition Commission (article 28, 29) because no established criteria by which the subject of purpose determines the winner among the five candidates proposed by the Commission the competition Commission (article 28, 29). Narrowed the right of persons to appeal against decisions of the competition Commission and the rights of civil servants to appeal against decisions of the head of the state service on the completion and termination of civil service, on imposing a disciplinary sanction, because NADS is deprived of the appropriate authority for handling such complaints and make demands to the state bodies and their officials about cancellation of decisions on issues of public service that are contrary to the legislation in terms of realization of citizens ' right to public service. Given the opportunity to appeal these decisions to court is not conducive to their timely resolution and significantly impedes the citizens of the constitutional rights and freedoms.</p> <p>3. Not created a legal framework for the implementation of the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On civil service" regarding the implementation of the contract on passage of civil service from 1 January 2020, respectively, making impossible its execution, because the order of conclusion of the contract on passage of public service with a person who is appointed to the position of public service, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine is not approved; not identified criteria for determining positions for the implementation of contractual forms of public service; the grounds for the termination of public service in the contract is not defined, and also provides that a contract may establish additional grounds for termination of public service (article 88-1), what can cause the violation of labor rights of civil servants and their arbitrary dismissals.</p> <p>4. The procedure for testing and determining the suitability of a civil servant for a position (Article 35) promotes discrimination against certain categories of employees, since the criteria for determining the suitability of candidates for the position are not established.</p> <p>5. The expulsion from the disciplinary commission of representatives of public associations, representatives of the elected body of the primary trade union organization from among civil servants or representatives of civil servants elected at a general meeting (conference) of civil servants (formerly) (Article 69) violates international standards conducting social dialogue.</p> <p>6. Reduction of the period of notice of change of essential working conditions to 30 days (Article 43), including certain grounds for change of essential conditions of civil service and conditions of termination of public service do not correspond to the recommendations of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe to the member states of the Council of Europe public servants in Europe "[3].</p> <p>7. The right of the subject to appoint a decision on the dismissal of a civil servant from the post of a civil service of category "A" is granted on his own initiative and at his own discretion, and not on the grounds specified in the law (Article 87-1), which will cause political arbitrariness.</p> <p>8. Contrary to the conventions and recommendations of the International Labor Organization, it is entitled to dismiss civil servants in the event of temporary disability (Article 87).</p>
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Environmental analysis involves evaluating innovations to identify potential threats and risks of adopting amendments to the Law on Civil Service of Ukraine [1, 2] and identifying potential opportunities for improving civil service legislation (Table 2).

Table 2.

Analysis of the external environment of evaluation of innovations of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" [1, 2].

O – Opportunities	T – Threats
<p>1. The modernization of the civil service and human resources management is carried out in accordance with the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement in accordance with the European standards of good</p>	<p>1. Leveling European values of protection of human rights and freedoms in the civil service, which contradicts the requirements of the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the EU.</p> <p>2. Neglect of norms of international standards of social dialogue in the sphere of social and labor relations in the civil service created</p>

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<p>administration, formulated in the SIGMA document "Principles of Public Administration", aimed at improving the quality and competitiveness of the civil service, oriented towards providing administrative services. services and improving the quality of life of the population and ensuring its development, taking into account European values, based on social dialogue and numbers technology.</p> <p>2. Implementation in the civil service of the European system of qualifications in the selection for civil service and its passing through the development and implementation of a sectoral framework of qualifications, development based on it professional standards in the civil service, based on which professional qualifications for a certain position and increased requirements for positions of public Category A, B, and B services, including relevant education and experience in a specific field or industry.</p> <p>3. Creation of a new system of evaluation of candidates for civil service positions, taking into account the requirements of professional standards.</p> <p>4. Improvement of the level of professionalism of civil servants through selection and passing of civil service in accordance with the requirements of professional standards, development of training programs for civil servants based on them, ensuring the functioning of a system of continuous education of civil servants on the basis of them, and taking into account the results of the assessment of their professional activity and personal needs to enhance professional competence, ensure effective professional activity, and achieve strategic goals and objectives ange the state body and the state as a whole.</p> <p>5. Creating conditions for online study of foreign language by civil servants.</p> <p>6. Restoration of the Institute of Personnel Reserve to senior management positions and creation of legal mechanisms for its effective use.</p>	<p>legal grounds for violation of labor rights of civil servants and their unjustified dismissal, promotes discrimination of civil servants and narrowing of the scope of their rights, prosperity of "arbitrariness". The lack of legal guarantees for the protection of civil servants from abuse of power reduced the level of protection of public servants in the exercise of their professional activity in the interests of the state.</p> <p>3. The established system of civil service management does not contribute to the proper formation and effective implementation of the state personnel policy.</p> <p>4. The low level of professionalism of civil servants and "staff shortages" in the state bodies is causing massive layoffs "objectionable" and selecting "new faces" without experience in the relevant field and special education. The proposed system of requirements to candidates for positions of public service is not conducive to their professional selection, because the requirements to persons applying for entry to the civil service, provide for posts "To" only having a higher education degree not lower than a Junior bachelor or bachelor by decision of the subject of appointment, fluency in the state language. Although employment in the public service category includes the positions of specialists and the main advisors in the Secretariat of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, Office of the President of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and other state bodies that require a high level of professionalism for the preparation of important documents, and making effective decisions regarding the functioning of the state.</p> <p>Among the requirements for employment in the public service category "A" and "B" cannot accommodate the requirements of presence of degree of the master of public administration, thereby not using an invaluable resource for masters in public administration prepared by the National Academy of public administration under the President of Ukraine (NAPA) and mastercourse public service under the state order, which is prepared of managers with vocational education, indicating inefficient use of budget funds, the depreciation of the role of the NADU as higher education institutions with special learning conditions, which are determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine (article 48). In addition, today the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine is not defined, and NAGA is not reformed.</p> <p>The definition in the Law of Ukraine "On civil service" one of the requirements for posts of category "A" – knowledge of foreign language, which is one of the official languages of the Council of Europe (i.e. English and French) contributes to the discrimination of civil servants and implementation of their constitutional rights, because it prevents the entry into the senior civil service is really professional and experienced managers who know the language insufficient for this level, or have studied another European language (German, Spanish, Italian, etc.).</p>
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3 Conclusions

Thus, the analysis of the internal and external environment allowed us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the innovations of the Law of Ukraine on Civil Service, as well as to identify their potential risks and threats, to identify opportunities for further improvement of the civil service legislation in order to eliminate them.

Among the potential threats and risks of these innovations are: the leveling of European values of protection of human rights and freedoms in the civil service, which contradicts the requirements of the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the EU; disregard for the norms of international standards of social dialogue in the

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field of social and labor relations in the civil service, which created the legal basis for violating the labor rights of civil servants and their unjustified dismissals, contributes to discrimination of civil servants and narrowing their scope of rights; lack of legal guarantees to protect public servants from abuse of power; inefficiency of the created system of management of the civil service, which does not contribute to the effective implementation of the state personnel policy; low level of professionalism of civil servants and “staff hunger” in state bodies, etc.

Potential opportunities for elimination of threats and risks in the civil service, which have arisen in connection with the amendments to the Law of Ukraine "About Civil Service" [1, 2], in our opinion, are:

1. Modernization of the civil service and human resources management in accordance with European standards of good administration, formulated in the SIGMA document “Principles of Public Administration”, aimed at improving the quality and competitiveness of the civil service, focused on providing quality administrative services and improving the quality of life of the population based on European values, based on social dialogue and digital technologies.

2. Implementation in the civil service of the European system of qualifications in the selection for civil service and its passing through the development and implementation of a sectoral framework of qualifications, development based on its professional standards in the civil service, based on which professional qualifications for a certain position and increased requirements for positions of public Category A, B, and B services, including relevant education and experience in a specific field or industry.

3. Creation of a new system of evaluation of candidates for civil service positions, taking into account the requirements of professional standards.

4. Improvement of the level of professionalism of civil servants through selection and passing of civil service in accordance with the requirements of professional standards, development of training programs for civil servants based on them, ensuring the functioning of a system of continuous education of civil servants on the basis of them, and taking into account the results of the assessment of their professional activity and personal needs to enhance professional competence, ensure effective professional activity, and achieve strategic goals and objectives of the state body and the state as a whole.

5. Creating conditions for learning foreign language by civil servants in online format.

6. Restoration of the Institute of Personnel Reserve to senior management positions and creation of legal mechanisms for its effective use.

The realization of potential opportunities to eliminate the created threats and risks in the civil service requires decisive action and concrete measures by amending the Law of Ukraine “About Civil Service” [2], namely:

1. To amend Article 13 of the Law on the renewal of the powers of the National Agency of Ukraine for Civil Service to carry out inspections of compliance with the legislation on public service; protection of the rights of civil servants in the adoption, passage and termination of the civil service, in particular with regard to appealing the decisions of the state bodies and sending requests to the state bodies and their officials to cancel the decisions on the civil service issues that contradict the legislation regarding the exercise by citizens of the right to public service.

2. To renew the powers of the Commission of the Senior Civil Service Corps by amending Articles 15 and 16 of the Law, with a view to creating preventive measures to avoid direct political influence when appointing candidates for civil service in category "A".

3. Strengthen requirements for civil service positions of categories "A" and "B" by amending Article 20 of the Law by providing for the posts of public service of categories "A" and "B" the availability of a master's degree of public administration, and for public service positions of category "V", that is not lower than a master's degree. In

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addition, the requirement for A category civil service posts to be a foreign language, which is one of the official languages of the Council of Europe, should be abolished, whilst creating the conditions for learning a foreign language while executing positions through training in relevant public procurement programs.

4. Improve the competition procedure by amending Articles 28, 29 of the Law by defining the criteria by which the nominee determines the winner of the five nominations submitted by the Commission, the selection committee.

5. Amend Art. 88-1 of the Law, providing additional grounds for termination of public service, which may be established in the contract. Develop and approve by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine the procedure for concluding a civil service contract with a person appointed to the position of civil service.

6. Amend Art. 35 of the Law, establishing criteria for determining the suitability of candidates for the position.

7. Amend Art. 69 of the Law, increasing the membership of the Disciplinary Commission to 6 persons, including representatives of public associations, representatives of the elected body of the primary trade union organization from among civil servants or representatives of civil servants elected at a general meeting (conference) of civil servants (as before) .

8. Amend Article 43 of the Law by defining the period and grounds for changing the essential conditions of the civil service and the conditions for termination of the civil service, taking into account the Recommendations of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe to the member states of the Council of Europe on the status of public servants in Europe.

9. Amend Article 87-1, providing for the grounds for the subject to make a decision on the dismissal of a civil servant from a public service category "A" on his own initiative.

10. To bring the norms of the Law of Ukraine "About Civil Service" concerning protection of civil servants, observance of their constitutional rights and freedoms in conformity with the conventions and recommendations of the International Labor Organization ratified by Ukraine.

11. To supplement the Law of Ukraine "About Civil Service" [2] with the article on introduction of personnel reserve for the posts of the senior civil service corps and the mechanisms of its use.

Thus, only Ukraine's adherence to international standards of civil service rights and freedoms will facilitate its modernization in the light of European values in order to create an effective system of public administration, accountable to the public, which works in the public interest, ensures the country's sustainable development and recognition in the international arena.

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